

The effect of hearing aids in King-Kopetzky Syndrome

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Abstract

King-Kopetzky syndrome is a neurological hearing disorder characterized by difficulty understanding speech (especially in an environment with background noise) despite a normal hearing threshold. In this study, we investigate whether the use of hearing aids helps to reduce symptom burden and achieve better functioning in daily life.

Introduction

King-Kopetzky syndrome is a neurological hearing disorder characterized by difficulty understanding speech (especially in an environment with background noise) despite a normal hearing threshold in otherwise healthy individuals. The syndrome is classified as an auditory processing and perception disorder. Patients suffering from King-Kopetzky syndrome describe hearing impairments in speech comprehension and show abnormal scores on the Social Hearing Handicap Index (SHHI) with normal or only slightly abnormal results on all common hearing tests. Although the syndrome was described by Samuel J. Kopetzky as early as 1948 and was further investigated by P.F. King in 1954, it is still little known outside the Anglo-Saxon scientific community. Nevertheless, up to 10% of all patients who consult a physician for hearing or speech issues are said to suffer from it.^{1,3-7}

The causes of King-Kopetzky syndrome are currently still a matter of scientific debate. However, there is increasing evidence that King-Kopetzky patients have a higher than average incidence of concurrent mild neuropsychiatric issues, including anxiety disorders and obsessive traits. Studies of familial clustering suggest hereditary factors (autosomal dominant) in some of the cases which contribute to the development of King-Kopetzky syndrome and neuropsychiatric disorders.¹⁷⁻²⁰

After ruling out other causes for a hearing or speech disorder, King-Kopetzky syndrome can be treated with targeted auditory training, stress reduction, sound amplification systems (e.g., in classrooms), treatment of any neurological symptoms that may be present, and with the use of regular hearing aids. If diagnosed in childhood, long-term consequences can be avoided by early treatment.^{14,18,19}

Method

172 patients (age 18 to 59; 90 men and 82 women) who had been prescribed digital hearing aids at least 10 years prior to the study because of King-Kopetzky syndrome (diagnosed in a large neurological clinic in South Africa) despite only a maximum hearing loss of 25 decibel bilaterally were compared with 159 patients with King-Kopetzky syndrome (age 19 to 62; 80 men and 79 women) who have never been prescribed hearing aids.

For this study, the patients completed a questionnaire with their ear, nose, and throat specialist or acoustician (see Appendix), which took into account not only the clinical but also the social situation of the patients. The identity of the patients remained unknown to the research group; only age, gender, comorbidities and duration of time with hearing aids were recorded as data directly related to the person. This study had no consequences for the treatment of the participating patients.

Results

It should be noted that bilateral digital hearing aids for King-Kopetzky syndrome patients are controversial among experts. Our study investigated this treatment option without a firm opinion on it.

1) How regularly do those fitted with hearing aids wear them in everyday life?

<i>Never</i>	4%
<i>0-2 hours per day</i>	12%
<i>3-5 hours per day</i>	08%
<i>6-8 hours per day</i>	11%
<i>8-12 hours per day</i>	41%
<i>From morning until bedtime</i>	24%

2) On a scale of 0 to 10, those fitted with hearing aids rated their usefulness as follows:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2%	4%	./.	./.	6%	4%	5%	14%	27%	21%	17%

3) Main reason to not wear hearing aids in the group of patients who found them useful:

<i>Social stigma</i>	82%
<i>Uncomfortable</i>	10%
<i>Other</i>	8%

4) Which type of hearing aid is subjectively more helpful?

<i>Analogue*</i>	42%
<i>Digital</i>	38%
<i>No difference</i>	20%

**In most countries only digital devices have been available since ~2010. The lifetime of a hearing aid is, when used normally, seven to ten years.*

5) Work situation of King-Kopetzky patients, fitted and not fitted with hearing aids

<i>King-Kopetzky patients with hearing aids and a job*</i>	79%
<i>King-Kopetzky patients with hearing aids and no job</i>	11%
<i>King-Kopetzky patients with hearing aids and no interest to have a job</i>	10%

<i>King-Kopetzky patients without hearing aids and a job*</i>	65%
<i>King-Kopetzky patients without hearing aids and no job</i>	21%
<i>King-Kopetzky patients without hearing aids and no interest to have a job</i>	14%

**The differences are statistically significant*

6) Reason for the treatment with hearing aids

<i>Recommendation of a neurologist</i>	89%
<i>Recommendation of a ENT specialist</i>	8%
<i>Own request (patient)</i>	3%

7) Most common comorbidities

<i>Speech disorders</i>	56%
<i>Anxiety disorders</i>	42%
<i>OCD</i>	12%
<i>Mild obsessive traits</i>	37%
<i>(Low IQ (>85))</i>	2%

Discussion

Despite normal hearing thresholds, bilateral provision of hearing aids is apparently a help for patients suffering from King-Kopetzky syndrome. Efficacy in our patient population was unexpectedly high, as was wearing time per day and compliance in general.

Surprising, and initially unexplainable, is the positive evaluation of analog hearing aids, which have not even been on the market in first world countries for about ten years. However, there were enough people in our patient collective who had experienced analog hearing aids themselves and could compare them directly with digital models. Digital hearing aids generally stand out as an advance in that they amplify only those frequency ranges that are impaired in the respective patient. Analog devices are, simply put, only volume enhancers. This leads to interesting questions regarding King-Kopetzky syndrome, which, however, are not the subject of this study. For example, it would need to be clarified whether the syndrome not only impairs speech understanding in isolation, but represents a broader auditory processing disorder.

Significant is also deviation regarding the occupational situation of the two groups. Even if causality could not be proven, a correlation between lack of hearing aid provision and unemployment is remarkable. Likewise, the fact that the initiative to prescribe bilateral

hearing aid fitting is mainly taken by neurologists, not by ear, nose and throat (ENT) specialists.

Conclusion

Based on our findings, the recommendation to prescribe bilateral hearing aids in patients with King-Kopetzky syndrome should be generous. There is no medical reason not to make hearing aids part of the standard treatment for King-Kopetzky syndrome despite social stigma, even if the audiogram does not show a drop in the hearing threshold to the range of a loss of 30 decibels or more. In addition, there appears to be a significant need for training among ENT physicians regarding King-Kopetzky syndrome. Finally, a question for further study is why analog hearing aids have such a strong acceptance in this patient group.

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No conflicts of interest.

Ethical standards, data safety compliance, patient's rights, and nature of this scientific work

This article is about the scientific classification of defined medical parameters to identify specific symptom clusters. It is not reporting on a clinical trial (or anything similar), especially not a prospective one. All participating subjects gave informed consent for their inclusion. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical, data protection, and patient rights requirements of the countries from which data were provided or in which these data were used for research purposes were complied with. The examination results of the participating patients were completely anonymized and transmitted to the study personnel with codes that could not be traced. Thus, at no time were personal data generated that could allow conclusions to be drawn about identities.

Raw data

While this study is in preprint status, raw data from this study is available upon request. Corresponding author is Dr. Balaskas. Appendixes etc. will be part of the print version.

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